
ANALYZING COHESIVE DEVICES AND DISCOURSE MARKERS

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Annotation: The article is about cohesive devices and discourse markers in English different texts. The research question is to define text forming functions of cohesion and coherence. The analysis of different kinds of texts done by the students presented in the article.

Key words: cohesive device, cohesion, reference, substitution, ellipsis, conjunction

Discourse structure refers to the way in which a whole text is organized. Teaching productive skills involves training the learners to structure their discourse so that it can fulfill its communicative purpose. Cohesive devices and discourse markers are used to organize written and spoken discourse.

Speakers and writers often use different devices to structure their discourse. These devices connect what they are saying to what they have said before, and to what they are going to say so that their overall message looks coherent and cohesive.

These devices can take different forms:

oIn spoken discourse, they are called discourse markers, because they mark out the beginning of a new ‘instance’ of discourse. These include well, oh, so, anyway, etc.

oIn written text, cohesive devices are used to create cohesion. This helps the text stick together, linking previous ideas with subsequent ones so that they can flow naturally. Examples of such cohesive devices are the use of linking words (e.g. because, but, however, nevertheless, moreover, etc...)

Halliday and Hassan [1] discuss Cohesion under five heads, reference, substitution, ellipsis, conjunction and lexical cohesion. But according to them, cohesion can be broadly classified as grammatical (reference, substitution, ellipsis) and lexical (reiteration, collocation). Halliday and Hassan keep conjunction on the borderline of the grammatical and lexical cohesion with the greater tilt on the grammatical side. Similar views are shared by Steffensen [2], Hatch [3] and Paltridge [4].

Following Halliday and Hassan, we will also be reviewing literature under the same five heads. Reference, in the words of Paltridge (2006), is the identity that an item of discourse reclaims through another item within or without the text.

Halliday and Hassan [1] also present a similar definition with a further explanation that when one item of the language appears second time in the discourse that is the continuity of reference.

Salkie [6], as well as Hatch [3], agree with Halliday and Hassan over the three types of cohesive references i.e. personal, demonstrative and comparative references. Apart from this, Halliday and Hassan remark that when the interpretation for the references is present in the text, it is called an endophoric reference, and when the interpretation lies outside the text, it is an exophoric reference. Halliday and Hassan further divide endophoric reference into anaphoric reference (looks back into the text) and cataphoric reference (looks forward into the text).

McCarthy [7], however, discards exophoric referents as truly cohesive because they are not the internal part of the text. While Halliday and Hassan explain that they play a role in the understanding of the text so they are cohesive. On the contrary, Paltridge [4] introduces another reference pattern too, that is, homophoric reference, for items which recover their identity through cultural knowledge. Substitution, simply, is ‘the replacement of one item by another’ remark Halliday and Hassan [1]. They find substitution to be a cohesive relation between wordings and not between the meanings, as is reference.

And Halliday and Hassan [1] present the following list of substitutes: Nominal: one, ones; same

Verbal: do

Clausal: so, not In addition.

Ellipsis, the third type of cohesive marker, as named by Hatch (1992), is a zero tie. Halliday and Hassan (1976) call it substitution by zero. Actually there is no tie in ellipsis and nothing substitutes but of course, like substitution, here too, something is left unsaid. Salkie (1995) makes it clear that every unsaid or left out expression cannot be considered an example of ellipsis. On the contrary, he writes, ellipsis is a gap or unsaid information that is known to the listener/reader of the text already, as it refers back to something already said. McCarthy (1991) also holds the same idea and he adds to it by mentioning that ellipsis is completely ‘a speaker choice made on a pragmatic assessment of the situation, not a compulsory feature when two clauses are joined together’. . Conjunctions can be defined best in the words of Cook (1989) as, the words which draw attention towards the relationships between sentences, clauses and words. McCarthy (1991) places conjunction among the grammatical cohesive devices, despite accepting it to be different from reference, substitution and ellipsis. He says, though it does refer to something backward or forward in the text, it still provides a relationship between the fragments of the language

In order to find out how karakalpak students awareness about text forming functions of coherence and cohesion we conducted a survey. The survey was

conducted among the 2nd year students of the English Linguistics chair. The purpose of the survey was to identify the most frequent and effective modes of written discourse analysis i.e. cohesion and coherence. Research question was to analyze in the texts of different kinds and to find out text forming functions of cohesion and coherence. The object of our investigation was different text types analysis of written discourse of Group 202 and Group 203.

Let’s discuss the sample of student’s analyzing written text. In this case instruction.

Personal letter

Dear Iroda,

I’m so desperate. I wish I hadn’t moved to this place. It’s not a bad place but it’s so quiet. If only there were more people here my age, then I wouldn’t feel so lonely. Even better, I wish my friends moved here from town. I thought I’d enjoy the quiet life of the village but now I wish there were some roads nearby so I could hear the traffic. I wish I could afford to move back to town but I don’t have the money. Maybe it is the weather. I wish it would stop raining so at least I could go for long walks in the fields. Sometimes, when I’m really sad, I wish the village disappeared or my house collapsed so that I’d have to move. Maybe it will get better. If only I would be more patient.

I wish I had written a more cheerful letter. It’s made me even sadder. I look forward to hearing from you with some suggestions.

Best wishes

Guli

Analysis

The text itself is clear and comprehensive. It consists of direct repetitions, antonyms, synonyms, hyponyms, reference pronouns, reference articles, ellipsis of clause elements, conjunctions, tense, reference.

Lexical cohesion

Direct repetition of content words: wish (lines 2,4,5,6,7,8,9 place (lines 2 quiet (3,4 move (2,4,5 village (5,8 could (6,7,8 town (4,6 so (2,3,4,5,7 maybe (7,9

Synonyms: field-place , patient-quiet,

Antonyms: more people- lonely, cheerful-sad, nearby-long walk

Hyponyms: town, place, village, field, desperate, lonely, sad, road-traffic

Here two words, cheerful and sad frequently occurring in the language as antonyms, and therefore incompatible, are to be interpreted as compatible description.

Grammatical cohesion

- Reference pronouns: I, this, my, it, me, you
- A subject personal pronoun: you, it, I
- An object personal pronoun: my, me

- Demonstrative pronoun: this
- Reference articles: a, the
- Ellipsis of clause elements: it’s not, I don’t have
- Conjunctions: so, but, then, when, or, so that
- Adversative conjunction: but
- Causative conjuncts: so, so that
- Temporal conjunctions: then, when
- from the same semantic field: town, place, village, field
- tense: present simple, past perfect, past simple
- exophoric reference: Maybe it’s the weather. I wish it would stop raining so at least I could go for long walks in the fields
- cataphoric reference: I’m so desperate. I wish I hadn’t moved to this place.
- Anaphoric reference: Sometimes, when I’m really sad, I wish the village disappeared or my house collapsed so that I’d have to move
- Noun: place people age, friend, town, life, village, roads, traffic, money, weather, field, house, letter, suggestions bad place=adjective+noun, cheerful letters=adjective+noun
- Adjectives: desperate, bad, quit, more, lonely, better, nearby, long, sad, patient, cheerful, sadder
- Verb: move, feel, enjoy, hear, afford, stop, go, disappear, collapse, get, made, look
- Prepositions: to, from, of, at, in, with
- Cohesive devices: if you want, it’s worth
- Hypothetical problem words: could

Advertisement

Clean and Clear is an amazing, new formula shampoo, that makes your hair stronger, thicker, better. If you suffer from weak and thin hair, this shampoo is exactly for you! With Clean and Clear your hair could be so soft and shiny. Your hair would always keep smooth even if you rub it with great force. Extra effort to make hair more attractive, impressive, bright and eye-catching. Result’s will be incredible. Hurry up! Let yourself shine.

Take it from us!

Analysis

Examples of lexical repetition include hair (five times, make, clear, clean(three times each. Also the words belonging to the same word family, i.e. words that share a common root: shine and shiny. The fact that these words are prominent is, of course, not accidental, since they carry the main thrust of the advertisement’s message. There are number of synonyms: amazing – incredible, attractive – impressive, shiny –

bright, effort – force, soft – smooth, as well as the antonyms strong – weak, thin – thick. Content item is shampoo and subtopic is hair.

Grammatical cohesion

- Reference pronouns: your, you, it, yourself, this
- A subject personal pronoun: you, it
- An object personal pronoun: your
- A reflexive pronoun :yourself
- A demonstrative pronoun :this
- Conjuncts: and, even if
- Additive conjuncts :and
- Adversative conjuncts: even if

It can refer forward and to a general idea, rather than to any specific word or clause, as in Take it from us. Take it from us demonstrates how some pronouns do not have referents in the text itself, but outside it.

Tense: Present Simple, Future Simple,

Anaphoric reference Results will be incredible.

Exaphoric reference Your hair would always keep smooth even if you rub it with great force.

Kataphoric reference Take it from us!

Cohesed devices if you, let yourself,

Roots clean- clear, shine – shiny

The text is made cohesive by a combination of lexical and grammatical devices.

In conclusion, analyzing a written and spoken text from the point of view to find out functions of coherence and cohesion is a complicated work. To make a good analysis for any kind of text we should work carefully. The given examples of analysis is done according to criteria and we think they are available for our students. Even though all students showed good efforts in analysing different kinds of texts in finding out the means of creating a cohesive and coherent text, teacher's guidance was still needed in terms of grammar, classifying information, and using the effective theme pattern so there will be no more excessive repetition or lacking a pattern in the text.

Refences:

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